

Thioureas from 8-amino-7-hydroxy-2-methylchromone

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The previous work^{1,2} on the synthesis of coumaryl thioureas have been extended to the chromone series as γ -pyrones are structurally related to coumarins and have been reported to possess marked pharmacological activities.³

In the present communication few substituted thioureas from 8-amino-7-hydroxy-2-methylchromone are described. 8-Amino-7-hydroxy-2-methylchromone was prepared

TABLE I

Thioureas from 8-amino-7-hydroxy-2-methylchromone

No.	R	Formula	M.P.*	Yield %	%Nitrogen		%Sulphur	
					Found	Reqd.	Found	Reqd.
1.	Ph	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ O ₃ N ₂ S	145°	50	8.40	8.58	9.60	9.81
2.	<i>o</i> -Tol	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ O ₃ N ₂ S	300°	52	8.10	8.23	9.20	9.41
3.	<i>m</i> -Tol	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ O ₃ N ₂ S	275°	55	8.25	8.23	9.23	9.41
4.	<i>p</i> -Tol	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ O ₃ N ₂ S	170°	56	8.06	8.23	9.30	9.41
5.	C ₆ H ₄ Cl (<i>o</i>)	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ O ₃ N ₂ ClS	300°	70	7.70	7.67	8.85	8.87
6.	C ₆ H ₄ Cl (<i>p</i>)	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ O ₃ N ₂ ClS	280°	75	7.60	7.76	8.61	8.87
7.	C ₆ H ₄ OMe (<i>o</i>)	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ O ₄ N ₂ S	300°	78	7.90	7.86	8.82	8.98
8.	C ₆ H ₄ OMe (<i>p</i>)	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ O ₄ N ₂ S	240°	80	7.75	7.86	8.82	8.98

*All melting points are uncorrected.

1. Kumar, Mathur, and Joshi, *This Journal*, 1965, **42**, 423.
2. Kumar, *Current Science*, (in press.)
3. Da Re, Verlicchi, Setnikar, Murmann, and Magistretti, *Nature*, 1959, **184**, 362; Da Re, Verlicchi, Setnikar, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1960, **25**, 1097; Klosa, *J. Prakt. Chem.*, 1963, **22**, 259; Jesthi, Sabat, and Rout, *This Journal*, 1965, **42**, 105; Highby, *J. Am. Pharm. Assoc.*, 1943, **32**, 74; Nakamura, Ota, and Fukuchi, *J. Pharm. Soc. Japan*, 1936, **56**, 68; Murti, Rao and Seshadri, *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci.*, 1947, **25A**, 22; 1948, **27A**, 33; Seshadri and Viswanadham, *ibid*, 1947, **25A**, 337.

by first nitrating 7-hydroxy-2-methylchromone and subsequently reducing the nitro compound formed by sodium hydrosulphite. Thioureas from this chromone were prepared by refluxing the ethanolic solution of amino chromone and arylisothiocyanates. In this way 8-amino-7-hydroxy-2-methylchromone gave with phenyl, *o*-tolyl-, *m*-tolyl-, *p*-tolyl-, *o*-chlorophenyl-, *p*-chlorophenyl-, *o*-methoxyphenyl and *p*-methoxyphenyl isothiocyanates the corresponding thioureas. They are reported in Table 1.

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